

SPACE ASTROMETRY

Evaluation of diffraction effects at the modulating grid

A revised optimisation of grid parameters and relay optics oversizing, considering also increased obstruction by the secondary mirror

L Lindegren, Lund Observatory 1979-12-13

0. Introduction

The modulating grid at the focal surface of the HIPPARCOS instrument is mainly characterised by two parameters: the grid period s (i.e. angular separation of adjacent slit centres) and the grid ratio $\delta = r/s$ (r being the width of each slit). Optimisation of the grid means choosing (s, δ) such that the expected photonstatistical mean error of the timing of the modulated signal is minimised for an instrument of given characteristics (pupil shape and size, spectral response curve) and light of a given spectral composition. Preliminary optimisations of this kind have been described in the AML Report (Vol. 2) and in various notes (e.g. Lindegren, 77-03-10, 77-04-04, 77-04-13, 77-06-15, 78-02-01, 79-02-20).

The present note gives a revised optimisation which takes into account previously neglected effects and revised data on several points:

- The entrance pupil is the two-split (asymmetric) rectangular one.
- Linear obstruction ratios in the range 0.45 - 0.60 are considered, in view of the possible necessity to introduce an internal baffle at the secondary mirror.
- The total instrument transmittance curve computed by MATRA (Nov. 1979), for silver coatings on mirrors and ordinary glass relay optics, is adopted.
- The effects of grid diffraction and finite relay optics acceptance angle are 'rigorously' taken into account according to my note of 79-09-19. The relay optics oversizing factor β is introduced as a possible third parameter for optimisation (with the practical

constraint $\beta \leq 1.5$).

There are two important conclusions to be drawn from this study:

(1) For a pupil length of $D = 0.25$ m, and practically independent of obstruction ratio, the optimum parameters are close to the following: $s = 1.1''$, $\delta = 0.36$, $\beta = 1.0$.

(2) Increasing the obstruction ratio from 0.45 to 0.60 increases the photonstatistical mean error by about 25 %. The rectangular entrance pupil is less sensitive to the increased obstruction than the previously considered semi-circular pupil.

1. Designations

$D = 0.25$ m	- full length of rectangular entrance pupil (along y axis)	
$W = 0.10$ m	- width of entrance pupil (along z axis)	
n	- entrance pupil obstruction ratio (linear)	
s	- grid period	
δ	- grid ratio (slit width/grid period)	
β	- relay optics oversizing factor (acceptance angle of relay optics normal to slits, normalised to the angular width of the undiffracted beam)	
λ	- wavelength of light	
F_λ	} Table 1	- monochromatic stellar flux (photons $s^{-1} m^{-2} nm^{-1}$)
T_λ		- instrument transmittance (telescope, grid support, relay)
Q_λ		- detector quantum efficiency
$k_c = 0.65$	- IDT electronic mesh transmittance	
$k_e = 0.90$	- discriminator counting efficiency	
$I_o = \langle I \rangle$	- average count rate	
M_1, M_2	- count rate modulation factors (1st and 2nd harmonics)	
σ	- mean error of the location of a star image in the grid frame, for an integration time of one second ($m_{pg} = 9.0$)	

2. Formulae

The intensity modulation at the detector level, expressed as the expected count rate (Hz) versus the modulation phase ψ (which goes through 2π rad as the star image is shifted one grid period) is

$$\begin{aligned} I(\psi) &= I_0 + I_1 \cos \psi + I_2 \cos 2\psi \\ &= I_0 (1 + M_1 \cos \psi + M_2 \cos 2\psi), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $M_k = I_k/I_0$ is the modulation factor of the k :th harmonic. Third and higher harmonics are neglected, and no phase shift is assumed between the first and second harmonics. The photonstatistical mean error for an integration time of one second is then given by

$$\sigma^{-2} = (2\pi/s)^2 I_0 \left\langle \frac{(M_1 \sin \psi + 2M_2 \sin 2\psi)^2}{1 + M_1 \cos \psi + M_2 \cos 2\psi} \right\rangle, \quad (2)$$

in which $\langle \rangle$ denote an average over one modulation period.

The harmonic components I_k are

$$I_k = DWk_c k_e \int d\lambda F_\lambda T_\lambda Q_\lambda E_\lambda^{(k)}, \quad (3)$$

where $E_\lambda^{(k)}$ are the monochromatic components

$$E_\lambda^{(k)} = \frac{1}{2}(2 - \delta_{0k}) \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} c_n c_{n-k} \int_{-\beta}^{\beta} H(x - \frac{2\lambda}{Ds}n, \frac{2\lambda}{Ds}k) dx. \quad (4)$$

The function H is

$$H(y, \xi) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } |y| > 1 \text{ or } |y + \xi| > 1; \text{ else} \\ 1 & \text{if } |y| > \eta \text{ and } |y + \xi| > \eta; \\ 1 - \eta & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

and c_n are the Fourier coefficients of the ideal grid:

$$c_n = \begin{cases} \delta & \text{for } n = 0; \\ \sin(n\pi\delta)/(n\pi) & \text{for } n \neq 0. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

For infinite relay optics oversizing, $\beta = \infty$, we note that the integral in (4) reduces to

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} H(x, \xi) dx = 2(1 - \eta^2) \text{MTF}(\xi), \quad (7)$$

where $MTF(\xi)$ is the normalized MTF of the ideal (aberration-free) telescope, in terms of normalized spatial frequency $\xi = 2\lambda k/Ds$. Eqs. (3) - (4) then reduce to the expression

$$I_k = (2 - \delta_{0k}) DW(1 - n^2)k_c k_e c_k \int d\lambda F_\lambda T_\lambda Q_\lambda MTF(2\lambda k/Ds), \quad (8)$$

which was used in previous calculations when the finite acceptance angle of the relay optics was neglected. It should be noted that $\sum_n c_n c_{n-k} = c_k$.

For finite oversizing the integral in (4) is easily evaluated analytically, since the primitive function is piecewise linear. Moreover, since H is zero outside a certain region, the sum over n needs only be taken for n between $\pm(\beta+1)Ds/2\lambda$. The numerical computation of $E_\lambda^{(k)}$ is thus exact. The integral in (3) and the average in (2) must however be evaluated by numerical methods; for the results reported in this note, the trapezoidal rule was used with step size 25 nm in λ and 15° in ψ . Results for $\beta = \infty$ were computed by means of (8).

The modulation factors M_1, M_2 computed by means of (3) and (8) are somewhat overestimated because optical aberrations, grid imperfections, and the finite sampling rate are neglected. To realistically account for these effects, the factors reported below and used in eq. (2) are computed from:

$$M_1 = 0.9 I_1/I_0 ; \quad M_2 = 0.8 I_2/I_0. \quad (9)$$

The degradation of M_1 will be almost entirely due to optical aberrations; a factor 0.9 corresponds to a total rms wavefront error of 25 nm or $\lambda/20$ at the effective wavelength $\lambda_{\text{eff}} = 500$ nm. Further degradation of M_2 is due to the sampling rate and grid defects (finite edge sharpness).

Computations are made for stars of different colours, roughly corresponding to $B-V = -0.25, 0.25, 0.75,$ and 1.25 , although it should be noted that stars as red as $B-V = 2.0$ will be encountered in reality. Adopted fluxes, transmittances, and quantum efficiencies are given in Table 1.

3. Results

3.1. Optimisation of relay optics oversizing (β)

Figs. 1a-c show how the average count rate $I_0 = \langle I \rangle$ and the modulation factors M_1 and M_2 depend on δ (grid ratio) and β (oversizing). Other parameters are kept at the following reference values:

obstruction ratio : $n = 0.45$
 grid period : $s = 1.1''$
 star colour : $B-V = 0.25$.

The count rate $\langle I \rangle$ is of course always increasing with β and δ , while M_1 and M_2 generally decrease slowly with increasing β or δ , at least for $\beta > 1$. However, the net effect in terms of the photonstatistical mean error σ (Fig. 1d) is to produce a minimum at $\beta = 1.00$ and $\delta \approx 0.35$.

The previously adopted grid ratio $\delta = 0.25$, which is the optimum value for infinite oversizing (i.e. neglecting grid diffraction), gives minimum mean error at $\beta \approx 1.9$, roughly in accordance with preliminary calculations in the note of 79-09-19. It is however slightly advantageous to reduce the oversizing and increase δ .

This is not a spurious result for this particular choice of n , s , and $B-V$. Exactly the same result for β is obtained for a much redder star ($B-V = 1.25$, Fig. 2a), a much larger obstruction ratio ($n = 0.60$, Fig. 2b), and other grid periods (not shown). For subsequent computations we adopt $\beta = 1.00$, i.e. no oversizing of the relay optics.

3.2. Optimisation of grid period (s) and grid ratio (δ)

Figs. 3a-d show the mean error for $B-V = 0.25$ versus s and δ ; the obstruction ratio is $n = 0.45, 0.50, 0.55, 0.60$, respectively.

For all n but the largest, the optimum combination is close to $s = 1.1''$, $\delta = 0.35$. For $n = 0.60$ one finds 1% smaller mean error with $s = 1.0$, $\delta = 0.40$ (note that the slit width $s\delta$ remains approximately the same).

Figs. 4a-c, together with Fig. 3c, show the effects of different colours; for $n = 0.55$ the optimum grid parameters are as follows (the mean errors should be compared with the value of σ used for computing the mean errors in Tables 5.1 and 5.2 in the revised 'Red Report', viz. $\sigma = 5.83$ marcsec):

Table 2. Optimum grid parameters versus colour for $\eta = 0.55$, $\beta = 1.00$.

B-V =	-0.25	0.25	0.75	1.25	
s_{opt} =	1.01	1.10	1.13	1.22	arcsec
δ_{opt} =	0.37	0.36	0.37	0.36	
σ_{min} =	5.80	5.35	4.99	4.35	marcsec

The final choice of (s, δ) must take into account the actual distribution of stars of different colours and the relative emphasis to be put on them; it must however be close to $s = 1.1''$, $\delta = 0.36$.

3.3. Accuracy as function of obstruction ratio (η)

Fig. 5 shows the relative photonstatistical mean error as a function of the linear obstruction ratio (η) and normalised to the present baseline $\eta = 0.44$. The solid lines are from the present computations (with $s = 1.1''$, $\delta = 0.35$, and $\beta = 1.0$). The dashed lines give, for comparison, the results on earlier computations in which the finite β was not taken into account:

- (a) is the somewhat academic result obtained for rectangular aperture, monochromatic light, and perfect tuning of grid parameters to the fundamental minimum of σ (note 77-03-10):

$$s_{\text{opt}} = 2\lambda/(1+\eta)D; \quad \delta_{\text{opt}} \text{ solved from the equation}$$

$$2\pi\delta = \tan(\pi\delta) + \sin(\pi\delta) \cos(\pi\delta)/(1+\eta); \quad (10)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{min}}^{-2} \propto (2\pi/s)^2 (1-\eta^2)\delta \left(1 - \left(1 - \left\{ \frac{\sin(\pi\delta)}{(1+\eta)\pi\delta} \right\}^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right).$$

- (b) is the result for polychromatic light (note 77-04-13, $\Delta\lambda/\lambda_{\text{eff}} = 0.47$) and $s = 2\lambda_{\text{eff}}/(1+\eta)D$, $\delta = 0.35$.

- (c) is the result for polychromatic light and semicircular aperture (note 79-02-20).

The present results are in reasonable agreement with the previous calculations for rectangular aperture (curves a and b), and the mean error goes up less steeply than for the circular aperture.

4. Conclusions

(1) The optimum relay optics oversizing is $\beta = 1.00$ for all obstruction ratios and colours. The choice of s and δ depends slightly on obstruction ratio and star colour, but $s = 1.1''$, $\delta = 0.36$ will always be a good compromise.

(2) The mean error with optimised (s, δ, β) increases with obstruction ratio η as shown in Fig. 5. As compared with previous computations, the mean error for the same obstruction ($\eta = 0.44$) is however smaller by about 25 %. This is due mostly to the more favourable transmittance function (T_λ), which reduces σ by about 14 %, but also to the improved optimisation of (δ, β), which reduces σ by about 9 %. An obstruction ratio of $\eta = 0.56$, as may be required for a baffle at the secondary mirror, would increase σ by 15 %, leaving us with a net advantage of 8 % in comparison with previous computations. The mean errors stated in the revised Red Report SCI(79)10 are thus compatible with $\eta = 0.56$ and a comfortable margin of more than 40 %.

Table 1. Adopted stellar fluxes, instrument transmittance, and detector quantum efficiency. Fluxes are in photons $s^{-1} m^{-2} nm^{-1}$ for blue mag. $B = 14$.

λ (nm)	F_λ				T_λ (MATRA)	Q_λ (S20)	(Bialko)	$\sum_n$ S11
	B-V = -0.25	0.25	0.75	1.25				
375	427	245	166	110	0.11	0.25	.25	.23
400	417	380	251	186	0.50	0.25	.25	.23
425	380	407	288	257	0.66	0.24	.23	.23
450	339	407	447	537	0.72	0.22	.22	.22
475	295	389	490	550	0.78	0.18	.18	.20
500	240	339	457	589	0.82	0.16	.15	.17
525	224	339	468	661	0.85	0.13	.11	.14
550	200	331	537	912	0.87	0.12	.07	.10
575	178	316	550	1047	0.86	0.10	.03	.04
600	162	295	525	977	0.84	0.08	.015	.03
625	141	282	550	1148	0.80	0.06	.005	.01
650	129	269	537	1202	0.75	0.05	0	0
675	117	257	550	1259	0.67	0.04		
700	107	245	550	1349	0.58	0.03		
725	98	229	525	1349	0.48	0.02		
750	91	224	525	1413	0.39	0.01		

OBSTR. RATIO = .45

B-V = .25

<I> [HZ] VS. BETA: S = 1.1

; DELTA =

FIGURE 1A

OBSTR. RATIO = .45

B-V = .25

M(1) VS. BETA; S = 1.1

; DELTA =

FIGURE 1B

OBSTR. RATIO = .45

B-V = .25

M(2) VS. BETA: S = 1.1

; DELTA =

FIGURE 1C

OBSTR. RATIO = .45

B-V = .25

M.E. (MARCS) VS. BETA: S = 1.1

; DELT

FIGURE 1D

OBSTR. RATIO = .45

B-V = 1.25

M.E. VS. BETA; S = 1.1

: DELTA =

FIGURE 2A

OBSTR. RATIO = .6

B-V = .25

M.E. VS. BETA; S = 1.1

; DELTA =

FIGURE 2B

OBSTR. RATIO = .45 B-V = .25
M.E. VS. DELTA; BETA = 1 ; S =

FIGURE 3A

OBSTR. RATIO = .5

B-V = .25

M.E. VS. DELTA: BETA = 1

S =

FIGURE 3B

OBSTR. RATIO = .55

B-V = .25

M.E. VS. DELTA: BETA = 1

; S =

FIGURE 3C

OBSTR. RATIO = .6

$\theta - V = .25$

M.E. VS. DELTA: BETA = 1 ; S =

FIGURE 3D

OBSTR. RATIO = .55

B-V = -.25

M.E. VS. DELTA; BETA = 1 ; S =

FIGURE 4A

OBSTR. RATIO = .55

B-V = .75

M.E. VS. DELTA; BETA = 1 ; S =

FIGURE 4B

OBSTR. RATIO = .55

B-V = 1.25

M.E. VS. DELTA: BETA = 1 ; S =

FIGURE 4C

FIGURE 5